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Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

MA. ROSALINA A. BESARIO, CPA, Ph.D.

Instructor II

Negros Oriental State University

besariorose@gmail.com

“MY LOVE STORY”

I once believed in long-term relationships. I had been in serious relationships that lasted anywhere from two to ten years. But everything changed when I suddenly married someone I had only known for a few days. There was no long courtship, no elaborate plans—we became a couple in just weeks.

That is when the problems began.

My mother was furious when I told my family about the whirlwind marriage. She couldn't accept my husband and, in her anger, went as far as disowning me. It was deeply painful, but I had to take responsibility—we had made the choice. At that time, I was already of age to make my own decisions, including marriage.

My mother's anger stemmed from the fact that she had relied on me to support my siblings through school. She believed everything would change now that I was married. Back then, she received my entire salary to help support our family. My husband was a seaman. After getting married, we made many beautiful plans for our future—how many children we'd have, what kind of house we'd build, the life we'd share. But then, suddenly, he fell ill.

At first, I thought it was just a simple illness. But it wasn't. It took ten long years for doctors to diagnose his condition finally. Imagine that—by then, our three children had already grown up. Yes, we still had three kids despite the mystery illness—funny how life works sometimes.

During those ten years, we visited nearly every medical specialist in Cebu. Still, no one could tell us what was wrong. He suffered from shortness of breath, vertigo, constant pain in his head, and frequent urination. He could barely sleep and began showing signs of anxiety and insomnia. A short walk outside would leave him breathless and dizzy. He couldn't even sit upright for more than an hour.

It was ten years of agony.

Many friends told me they would have walked away if they had been in my place. But I always said, when we got married and exchanged vows, we promised: "...in sickness and in health, till death do us part." That was my promise—and I meant every word. I loved my husband.

Then, one day, something unexpected happened. While listening to an afternoon program on an AM radio station, my husband heard a caller describing symptoms almost exactly like his. He paid close attention as the anchorwoman gave advice and mentioned a certain doctor. Without hesitation, he sought out that doctor. And finally—miraculously—that doctor found the problem.

We had him admitted to a well-known hospital in Cebu and proceeded with all the necessary examinations and workups. After just a month, there were clear signs of improvement. Slowly but surely, my husband recovered. Today, he is entirely well.

He never achieved his dream of becoming a ship captain. But in many ways, he became something even greater—a captain of his family's dreams. We now run our own family business, and we are building the life we once only imagined. Sometimes, even when we think we're in control, God takes the wheel and steers us in a different direction. We may not always understand the journey, but we must trust Him.

What we want for ourselves may not be what He has planned—and that's okay. In all things, we must place Him first.

